

GENERATION AND RELAXATION OF THERMAL STRESSES IN METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The internal thermal stresses in Al-SiC composites are studied at volume fractions of 5, 10 and 15%. Thermal cycling loops are measured from 20°C to maximum temperatures of 100, 200, 300 and 400°C; the strains in the phases are measured directly by neutron diffraction. Calculations of strains by FEM techniques are based on a thermo-plastic model with temperature dependent properties for the Al-matrix. The thermal cycling loops show semi-quantitative agreement between experiments and calculations with the best fit at high volume fractions. Generally the numerical values of phase strains are smaller for experiments than for calculations, which indicate that relaxation processes take place. These are governed by the numerical level of strains, and promoted by the elevated temperatures.

INTRODUCTION

The inherent mismatch in thermal expansion coefficients and in mechanical properties between matrix and inclusions in common composites, causes the build up of mismatch stresses during the production of the composites, as well as under subsequent service conditions e.g. involving thermal loading. These mismatch stresses may modify the mechanical properties of the composite structure in service, and it is hence of interest to determine the residual stresses generated during the production of the material, and subsequently to determine the generation and possible relaxation of such stresses under service conditions. Such studies are performed on metal matrix composites (MMC) where stresses can easily be determined by neutron diffraction techniques. FEM modeling [1] is an attractive tool for the simulation of fiber/matrix interactions, and as such it provides valuable insight into detailed continuum mechanics based predictions of stress and strain contours around individual inclusions. The generation of residual stresses during the final cooling process in the production can hence be simulated, as well as the subsequent generation during e.g. thermal cycling. Such simulations, however, render results at a dimensional scale at which quantitative experimental evaluation of the numerical predictions is difficult. Volume averages are, however, readily deduced from the detailed numerical results, and such volume averages of elastic strains in the matrix and in the inclusions can be evaluated experimentally by neutron diffraction [2,3]. It is the primary goal of the present investigation, to combine the novel experimental technique of neutron diffraction with the powerful numerical FEM technique, in order to evaluate the generation and possible relaxation of thermal stresses in a MMC model system consisting of silicon carbide whiskers embedded in an aluminium matrix.

MATERIALS CHARACTERIZATION

The materials used are aluminium composites containing 5, 10 and 15% by volume of SiC whiskers (SiC_w). They are fabricated by powder blending, consolidation and extrusion [4]. The extrusion temperature is 500°C. The atomised aluminium powder has a mean diameter of 6 μm and contains not more than 0.26 wt% Fe and 0.18 wt% Si. The oxide from the surface of the Al powder appears in the composite material as fine Al₂O₃ particles of about 0.8% by volume. The SiC_w, supplied by Mandoval Ltd., UK, consist of cubic single crystals, and have a mean diameter of ~1 μm and a mean aspect ratio of about 20. As a result of the fabrication process the aspect ratio of SiC_w in the extruded composites is reduced to about 7. The distribution of the SiC_w in the composites is fairly uniform. Approximately 60 vol% of the SiC_w are aligned within 10° from the extrusion axis.

The temperature dependent mechanical properties of the un-reinforced aluminium over a large strain range (up to a true strain of about 0.9) have been evaluated by compression tests. The experimental data for the temperature range from 20 to 500°C are fitted to a Voce type constitutive equation, and the resulting stress-strain curves are shown in Fig.1.

Figure 1. Temperature dependent elastic-plastic behavior of the aluminium matrix material.

NEUTRON DIFFRACTION EXPERIMENTS

The diffraction technique allows the monitoring of the individual phase responses by focusing on selected sub-sets of crystallites having appropriate lattice parameters for the fulfillment of the Bragg condition. In the present experiments the Al₁₁₁ and SiC₁₁₁ reflections are used as embedded "strain gauges" reflecting measures of the volume averages of matrix and inclusion elastic strains. The accuracy in determining elastic lattice strains by this approach is typically better than $\pm 100 \times 10^{-6}$.

The initial thermally induced residual strains are characterized by comparing Al₁₁₁ and SiC₁₁₁ lattice parameters as measured in the composite, with the Al₁₁₁ lattice parameter measured in an extruded test sample of the un-reinforced Al-matrix material and with the SiC₁₁₁ lattice parameter measured in a "powder sample" of free silicon carbide whiskers contained in a quartz tube during measurements.

For the subsequent thermal cyclic loading, uniaxial test specimens are mounted in the loading device for in-situ straining of test specimens. While kept under load control at zero load, samples are heated by infrared line heaters at a rate of approximately 100°C/min. to levels of 100, 200, 300 and 400°C. At each temperature level the neutron diffraction measurements are halted for approximately 2 minutes for the sample temperature to stabilize, whereafter the lattice parameters are monitored successively over periods of time reaching from 2 to 6 hours. Samples are subsequently allowed to cool to 20°C over approximately 30-40 minutes, and the monitoring of lattice parameters is continued at 20°C over periods of time reaching from 2 to 6 hours. The matrix and inclusion responses are monitored in separate samples in order to optimize the time resolution in studying the relaxation of internal strains. Currently this means that lattice parameters are monitored at intervals of approximately 5-7 minutes.

FINITE ELEMENT MODELING

The FEM modeling is a 2D axi-symmetric approach using the commercially available FEM code SOLVIA. The models shown in Fig 2. consist of 200 eight noded plane elements for the matrix and 96 similar elements for the inclusion.

Figure 2. FEM models used for the axi-symmetric simulations of the composite, left to right: $V_f = 5, 10$ and 15%. In the simulations the free top end and right hand edge of the models are kept straight by imposed nodal displacement constraints.

The matrix is idealized as a bilinear elastic/plastic and isotropic hardening material having temperature dependent properties as given in Table 1., while the silicon carbide inclusions are modeled as purely elastic with no temperature dependent variation of the Young's modulus. The temperature dependent properties of the matrix material are determined experimentally as described above. Some uncertainty exists as regards to the modulus of the various forms of silicon carbide used as reinforcements. In the present investigation we choose to base the value of the SiC whisker modulus on the comparison between the composite modulus as determined by traditional tensile tests, and an imposed uniaxial elastic loading of the FEM models. Using a Young's modulus of 206 GPa in the FEM simulation, the composite stiffness closely agrees with the actual observations from tensile test, hence 206 GPa is here taken as our best estimate of the correct SiC modulus. It should be mentioned that by this approach we neglect any effects of whisker mis-alignment.

The materials model does at present not include visco-plastic properties to describe a possible rate dependency, and neither does it include any description reflecting relaxation phenomena such as diffusion.

Table 1. Materials properties used in the FEM model simulations. The matrix material is modeled as a bilinear elastic plastic material with temperature dependent properties (the slope of the plastic part is the tangent modulus E^T), whereas the inclusions are modeled as elastic with no temperature dependency of the modulus.

T [°C]	Phase	E [GPa]	ν	σ_y [MPa]	E^T [GPa]	α [$10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}$]
20	Al matrix	70	0.33	163	46	25.8
100	Al matrix	45	0.33	125	21	25.8
200	Al matrix	35	0.33	95	10	25.8
300	Al matrix	30	0.33	69	5	25.8
400	Al matrix	25	0.33	53	-9	25.8
500	Al-matrix	20	0.33	39	-12	25.8
20-500	SiC-inclusions	206	0.20	xxxx	xxxx	3.9

Thermal loading is imposed on all nodes simultaneously from an estimated stress-free temperature of 500°C, simulating the cooling process from the extrusion temperature to a room temperature of 20°C. Based on the data in Fig. 1., it is reasonable that 500°C can be taken as the stress-free temperature due to the very low yield stress of aluminium at temperatures above 500°C. Subsequently the thermal cyclic loadings to 100, 200, 300 and 400°C are simulated for comparison with the neutron diffraction experiments.

FEM codes typically provide results (either nodal or integration point results) in terms of displacements, total strains, plastic strains and stresses, while the pure elastic part of the accumulated strains are not directly available. The elastic strains are hence deduced from the stresses through Hooke's law, and volume averages are readily calculated through the mean element stresses weighted by the proper element volumes.

THERMAL CYCLIC RESPONSE

The initial thermal residual strains in the matrix and in the inclusions, as measured by neutron diffraction, are found to depend on the volume fraction of inclusions. The data are shown in Fig. 3 and 4 as the starting points (A) for the thermal cycling loops.

The present FEM predictions exaggerates the numerical value of the residual strains remaining upon reaching 20°C when cooling from the extrusion temperature of 500°C. Hence a continuation of the FEM simulations by cycling the models to the same temperatures as for the neutron diffraction experiments, does unavoidably initiate at a strain level different from those observed in the real composite. However, the continuation of the simulations during cyclic thermal loading, is here used to visualize the thermal strain loops expected based on thermo-plastic matrix properties. Thus the FEM predicted loops, as shown in Fig. 3 and 4, will differ from the experimentally determined loops by levels, which can be attributed to rate dependency and possible relaxation by diffusion.

The neutron diffraction data are presented in Fig. 3 and 4 in terms of symbols indicating the initial residual strain levels (A), the strain levels monitored 2 minutes after reaching the elevated temperature level (C), the strain levels monitored following a holding time of some hours at the

elevated temperature level (D), the strain levels monitored following a 30-40 minutes cooling period to 20°C (F) and the strain levels monitored following a holding time of some hours at 20°C (G).

DISCUSSION

The initial matrix and inclusion strain levels (point A) are the identical starting points of all thermal loops describing a given volume fraction of inclusions. These initial strain levels are predicted numerically by FEM simulations of the cooling processes from 500°C using the thermo-plastic behavior of the matrix shown in Fig. 1.

Focusing on the inclusion response as indicated by (●) in Fig.3 and 4, this initial strain level is well predicted for $V_f=15\%$, whereas some discrepancy is observed for the lower volume fractions. Here measured strain levels are numerically lower than the predictions indicating higher degrees of relaxation. This is justified by the fact that the numerically higher strain levels expected in the inclusions of the lower volume fraction materials, provide higher driving forces for relaxation.

Heating to the elevated temperature T_{max} (point C and D) it is observed that for all levels of T_{max} also this level is well predicted by FEM for $V_f=15\%$. The correspondence is more moderate for the lower volume fractions; however, it is observed, that the numerical shift in inclusion strains due to the temperature change is very well predicted.

The discrepancy at T_{max} is hence mainly attributed to the differences in the initial level of strains (point A). It is interesting to note that whereas the discrepancies at 20°C (point A) are attributed to relaxation, with increasing relaxation with increasing levels of strain, then upon heating to T_{max} strain levels approach zero, where there are no driving force for relaxation, and hence strain levels are well predicted by FEM-simulations excluding relaxation phenomena.

Cooling from T_{max} to 20°C the observed strain levels (point F and G) are in general numerically higher than the FEM predictions. In most cases this unexpected kind of discrepancy is increased when FEM predictions are simply displaced to initiate at the levels observed at T_{max} immediately before reversing the temperature (point D).

Focusing on the matrix response as indicated by (▲) in Fig. 3 and 4, these initial strain levels are moderately well predicted, though not as accurate as for the inclusion response. The initial strain levels in the matrix appear to be more affected by relaxation phenomena than those in the inclusions. Furthermore the trend is that for the higher volume fractions the discrepancy is larger as the higher strain levels predicted by the FEM simulations promote the relaxation.

Heating to the elevated temperature T_{max} (point C and D) it is observed that for all volume fractions this level is moderately well predicted by FEM. It is observed, that the numerical shift in matrix strains due to the temperature change is very well predicted for $T_{max}=100$ and 200°C, where the final levels of strain (point C and D) are near zero. Hence the small strains give only limited driving force for relaxation, and FEM predictions neglecting relaxation, correspond well with the experimental data. The discrepancy at T_{max} is hence mainly attributed to the differences in the initial level of strains (point A). For $T_{max}=300$ and 400°C FEM calculations predict higher numerical strain levels than observed by neutron diffraction. This is justified by the fact that strain levels build up to quite high levels, which combined with the higher temperature promote relaxation phenomena not included in the FEM simulations.

Figure 3. Thermal cycling loops for the three volume fractions of inclusions; a-c: 20-100-20°C and d-f : 20-200-20°C. The thermal loops as determined by neutron diffraction are shown by the points A-G, with the FEM predictions shown in full lines.

Figure 4. Thermal cycling loops for the three volume fractions of inclusions; a-c: 20-300-20°C and d-f : 20-400-20°C. The thermal loops as determined by neutron diffraction are shown by the points A-G, with the FEM predictions shown in full lines.

Cooling from T_{\max} to 20°C the observed strain levels (point F and G) are moderately well predicted for $V_f=15\%$. As for the heating process, the numerical shift in matrix strains due to the temperature change is very well predicted for $T_{\max}=100$ and 200°C , where the final levels of strain (point F and G) at 20°C are relatively small. Hence, there is only limited driving force for relaxation. The discrepancy at T_{\max} is hence mainly attributed to the differences in the initial level of strains (point D). For $T_{\max}=300$ and 400°C FEM calculations predict higher numerical strain levels than observed by neutron diffraction. As for the heating process, this is justified by the fact that strains build up to quite high levels, which promote relaxation phenomena not included in the FEM simulations. For $V_f=5$ and 10% similar trends are seen though not as clearly as for the high volume fraction of inclusions.

SUMMARY

The present study addresses the generation and relaxation of internal stresses in MMC's, and analyses the phenomena by direct experimental measurements of internal strains in the two phases and by FEM calculations of the composite using a thermo-plastic model based on temperature dependent elastic and plastic matrix properties. The thermal cycling is described with semi-quantitative agreement between experiments and modeling, both in trends of the cyclic performance and in the numerical values. All discrepancies are within a range of at most $\pm 2-300 \times 10^{-6}$, and most experimental values are numerically closer to zero than the FEM calculations, indicating the degree of relaxation unaccounted for in the thermo-plastic model. The agreement between measurements and FEM calculations is generally better for the high volume fraction ($V_f=15\%$) of fibers, probably due to more stable internal microstructure and stresses. The temperature dependent matrix properties impose curved lines in the thermal loops, in contrast to previous calculations based on constant matrix properties, equal to those at 20°C , which gives straight lines in the thermal loops.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work was carried out at The Engineering Science Center for Characterization and Modeling of Materials within Risø National Laboratory.

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